

Highly Scalable Personalized Treatment Recommendation in Critical Care

Chandra Prasetyo Utomo
Department of Informatics
Universitas YARSI
Jakarta, Indonesia
chandra.prasetyo@yarsi.ac.id

Kohei Ichikawa
Division of Information Science
Nara Institute of Science and Technology
Nara, Japan
ichikawa@is.naist.jp

Soratouch Pornmaneerattanatri
Division of Information Science
Nara Institute of Science and Technology
Nara, Japan
pornmaneerattanatri.so.pn8@is.naist.jp

Kundjanasith Thonglek
Applied Information Systems Research Division
Osaka University
Osaka, Japan
thonglek.kundjanasith.cmc@osaka-u.ac.jp

Nashuha Insani
Department of Informatics
Universitas YARSI
Jakarta, Indonesia
nashuha.insani@students.yarsi.ac.id

Martha Riskiaty
Department of Informatics
Universitas YARSI
Jakarta, Indonesia
martha.riskiaty@students.yarsi.ac.id

Abstract—Universitas YARSI and Nara Institute of Science and Technology (NAIST) are collaborating on a project focused on developing machine learning models for medical healthcare. In an era where personalized medicine is becoming increasingly important, the project aims to establish new treatment methods that effectively utilize both edge computing and cloud computing technologies in machine learning.

A key focus of this collaboration is optimizing patient care in Intensive Care Units (ICUs). The project's goal is to build a reinforcement learning model that maximizes patient survival probability. This model will be based on the analysis of time-series vital data and medical treatment records obtained from ICU patients.

One of the challenges of the project is the need to finely cluster a vast number of patients based on their vital data and responses to medical treatments. Subsequently, the optimal medical treatment for each cluster needs to be determined. To achieve this, extensive parallel computing is essential for clustering based on numerous parameters and for the optimization of the corresponding reinforcement learning models.

In addressing these challenges, YARSI is primarily responsible for developing the algorithms for the reinforcement learning model construction. Meanwhile, NAIST is focusing on optimizing these processes on distributed systems.

Index Terms—reinforcement learning, parallel computing, distributed systems, critical care, personalized medicine